

Comparison of Carotid Intima Media Thickness and Diabetic Retinopathy in Patients of Type II Diabetes MellitusVaibhav Bisne¹, Shailendra Mane², Rajesh J. Khyalappa³¹Junior Resident 3, Department of Medicine, Dr. D. Y. Patil Medical College, Hospital and research institute, Kadamwadi Kolhapur, Maharashtra, India²Professor, Department of Medicine, Dr. D. Y. Patil Medical College Hospital and Research Institute Kolhapur³Vice Dean Professor & Head, Department of General Medicine, Dr. D.Y. Patil Medical College, Hospital & Research Institute, Kadamwadi, Kolhapur

Received: 25-06-2024 / Revised: 23-07-2024 / Accepted: 26-08-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: Diabetes mellitus is the leading cause of end-stage renal disease, non-traumatic lower-limb amputation, and blindness. Furthermore, diabetic retinopathy (DR) is the primary cause of visual impairment worldwide. Another complication stemming from diabetes is generalized atherosclerosis, which may manifest as ischemic heart disease, cerebrovascular accidents, or peripheral vascular disease. Utilizing CIMT measurements has been instrumental in predicting cardiovascular outcomes in diabetic patients.

Materials and Methods: This observational, cross-sectional study was conducted in tertiary care Hospital and, Kolhapur over a period of 24 months after institutional ethical committee approval. A total of 121 patients satisfying the below inclusion and exclusion criteria were involved in the study.

Results: The gender distribution of the study population showed a predominance of males (67.8%) compared to females (32.2%). The mean age was 54.83 years, indicating a middle-aged population. This age group is often associated with an increased risk of chronic diseases such as diabetes and hypertension. The mean CIMT on the right side (CIMT(R)) was 0.8802 mm, while on the left side (CIMT(L)), it was 0.8620 mm, indicating slightly higher measurements on the right side. Subjects with non-proliferative diabetic retinopathy (NPDR) had higher mean CIMT values (0.9436 mm on the right and 0.91 mm on the left) compared to those without retinopathy (0.8346 mm on the right and 0.82 mm on the left). Those with proliferative diabetic retinopathy (PDR) exhibited even higher values (1.1500 mm on the right and 1.00 mm on the left).

Conclusion: The present study provides valuable insights into the gender distribution, demographic and clinical parameters, and prevalence of chronic diseases in a population with Type II Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM). The associations between increased CIMT, diabetic retinopathy, poor glycemic control, and demographic factors underscore the need for comprehensive and personalized management strategies to mitigate the risk of complications in T2DM patients. CIMT, being a non-invasive procedure, should be incorporated into routine examinations of type 2 DM patients at least once or twice a year to look for atherosclerotic changes.

Keywords: Carotid Intima Media Thickness, Diabetic Retinopathy, Type II Diabetes Mellitus.

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Introduction

Diabetes mellitus stands as the leading cause of end-stage renal disease, non-traumatic lower-limb amputation, and blindness. Additionally, diabetic retinopathy (DR) ranks as the primary cause of visual impairment globally. The prevalence of DR escalates with the duration of diabetes.

Other factors contributing to DR development encompass inadequate glycemic control, diabetes type, and the presence of concurrent conditions like dyslipidemia, hypertension, smoking, pregnancy, and nephropathy. [1] Retinopathy serves as a crucial diagnostic indicator for diabetic

nephropathy, manifesting in approximately 90% and 60% of patients with type 1 and type 2 diabetes, respectively. [2] Given the potential rapid progression of retinopathy and the beneficial effects of treatment in slowing disease advancement, regular screening of diabetic patients for retinopathy development is crucial.

For individuals with type 1 diabetes, screening should commence after five years of diagnosis, while for those with type 2 diabetes, it should begin at the time of diagnosis and continue annually thereafter for retinopathy assessment. [3] Another

complication stemming from diabetes is generalized atherosclerosis, which may manifest as ischemic heart disease, cerebrovascular accidents, or peripheral vascular disease. Detecting diabetic atherosclerosis often involves measuring the intima-media thickness (IMT) of the common or internal carotid artery. Utilizing CIMT measurements has been instrumental in predicting cardiovascular outcomes in diabetic patients. [4]

Elevations in carotid IMT have been linked to a heightened risk of myocardial infarction and stroke among elderly individuals lacking a history of cardiovascular disease. [5] The mean carotid intima-media thickness (CIMT) has been identified as a dependable indicator of the risk of ischemic stroke in individuals with type 2 diabetes, offering a straightforward and non-invasive screening method for evaluating atherosclerosis in this patient population. [6] By elucidating the relationship between these markers, the research seeks to enhance cardiovascular risk assessment and inform more effective screening and prevention strategies for patients with T2DM.

So the aim of this study was to compare CIMT and DR in patients of type II diabetes mellitus.

Methodology

This observational, cross-sectional study was conducted in Dr. D.Y Patil Medical College Hospital and Research Institute, Kolhapur over a period of 24 months after institutional ethical committee approval. A total of 121 patients satisfying the below inclusion and exclusion criteria were involved in the study. Inclusion criteria All type 2 diabetes mellitus patients, diagnosis of Diabetes, fasting Plasma Glucose $\geq$ 126 mg/dl, 2 hours post 75g Glucose $\geq$ 200 mg/dl, HbA1c $\geq$ 6.5% Exclusion criteria Overt renal failure, type 1 Diabetes.

Patients included in this study were with diagnosed diabetes mellitus based on the inclusion criteria, valid, written, informed consent were taken in patient's own language, all the study participants were underwent B-mode ultrasonography scan of bilateral extracranial carotid arteries.

On-admission values of fasting blood sugar, post prandial blood sugar, HbA1c, lipid profile of these patients were collected from their records, all data was entered in Microsoft Excel and then analyzed. carotid Intima Media thickness was measured by B mode ultrasound having an electric transducer with a mid-frequency of 7.5 mHz, scans were performed on both extracranial carotid arteries.

Results

Table 1: Gender distribution of study population

Gender	Frequency N (%)
z	
Males	82(67.8)
Females	39(32.2)
Total	121(100)

Table no 1 shows the gender distribution of the study population showed a predominance of males (67.8%) compared to females (32.2%).

Table 2: Mean distribution of demographic and clinical parameters of study population.

Demographic and clinical parameters	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age	25	84	54.83	13.13
Weight	48.00	92.00	69.72	11.014
BMI	18.20	35.60	25.57	4.09
Waist-Hip ratio	0.00	1.38	0.86	0.12
Duration of DM	1.00	22.00	7.6612	3.74512
CHL	189	239.00	215.11	14.92
TGL	100	180.00	138.62	24.09
VLDL	7.00	30.00	17.66	7.29
HDL	21.00	35.00	28.80	4.28
LDL	110.00	140.00	124.16	8.71
CHL/HDL	5.46	10.82	7.63	1.24
LDH/HDL	3.17	6.27	4.41	0.77
HbA1c	3.50	13.20	8.11	1.54
Fasting Blood Sugar (mg/dl)	120.00	393.00	186.71	59.08
Postprandial Blood Sugar (mg/dl)	151.00	522.00	264.90	61.76

BMI – Basal metabolic Rate FBS -Fasting Blood Sugar (mg/dl), PPBS - Postprandial Blood Sugar (mg/dl), CHL-Cholesterol, TGL-Triglycerides,

VLDL-Very Low-Density Lipoproteins, HDL-High Density Lipoproteins, LDL -Low Density Lipoproteins CHL/HDL- Cholesterol /High density

lipoproteins, LDH/HDL- Low Density Lipoprotein/ High density lipoproteins, HbA1c-Glycated Haemoglobin

Table no 2 Shows Mean Distribution of Demographic and Clinical Parameters The mean distribution of demographic and clinical parameters

provides insights into the health status of the study population.

The mean age was 54.83 years, indicating a middle-aged population. This age group is often associated with an increased risk of chronic diseases such as diabetes and hypertension.

Graph 1: Stratification of subjects according to age groups

Graph no 1 shows stratification of Subjects According to Age Groups the stratification of subjects according to age groups revealed that the majority of the study population was aged between

46-65 years, accounting for nearly half of the participants. This age distribution is typical for studies on chronic diseases, as the prevalence tends to increase with age.

Table 3: Mean differences of carotid Intima thickness based on location.

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
CIMT(R)	0.70	1.20	0.8802	0.11946
CIMT(L)	0.70	1.10	0.8620	0.08292

CIMT(R)- Carotid Intima Media Thickness (Right side) CIMT(L) - Carotid Intima Media Thickness (Left side) CIMT(R)- Carotid Intima Media Thickness (Right side) CIMT(L) - Carotid Intima Media Thickness (Left side), NPDR-Non-Proliferative Diabetes Retinopathy, PDR-Proliferative Diabetes Retinopathy. Table no 3 shows Mean Differences of Carotid Intima

Thickness Based on Location the mean differences in carotid intima-media thickness (CIMT) based on location are crucial for understanding cardiovascular risk factors in different populations. The mean CIMT on the right side (CIMT(R)) was 0.8802 mm, while on the left side (CIMT(L)), it was 0.8620 mm, indicating slightly higher measurements on the right side.

Graph 2: Mean CIMT findings in fundus

Comparison of Carotid Intima Thickness in Subjects with and Without Retinopathy: The comparison of CIMT in subjects with and without retinopathy revealed significant differences. Subjects with non-proliferative diabetic retinopathy (NPDR) had higher mean CIMT values (0.9436

mm on the right and 0.91 mm on the left) compared to those without retinopathy (0.8346 mm on the right and 0.82 mm on the left). Those with proliferative diabetic retinopathy (PDR) exhibited even higher values (1.1500 mm on the right and 1.00 mm on the left).

Graph 3: Funduscopy findings of subject's gender wise

NPDR-Non-Proliferative Diabetes Retinopathy, PDR- Proliferative Diabetes Retinopathy

Gender Differences of Fundus Findings: The gender differences in fundus findings showed that males had a higher proportion of normal fundus (73.2%) compared to females (46.2%). However, females exhibited a higher prevalence of NPDR (46.2%) and PDR (7.7%) than males (25.6% NPDR and 1.2% PDR).

Graph4: Funduscopy findings in age groups

Age Distribution of Population in Funduscopy Findings: The age distribution of the population in funduscopy findings indicates a higher prevalence of normal fundus in younger age groups and an

increasing incidence of diabetic retinopathy (NPDR and PDR) with advancing age. This trend is consistent with several recent studies examining the relationship between age and diabetic retinopathy.

Table 4: Mean Fundus differences of Demographic and clinical parameters of study subjects.

	NORMAL		NPDR		PDR		F-value	P-value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Age	52.26	13.41	58.5	4.72	63.50	13.98	4.658	0.011
Weight	69.56	11.70	75.5	5.50	62.50	10.24	1.054	0.352
BMI	25.69	4.14	28.57	1.43	22.82	4.60	0.936	0.395
Waist-Hip ratio	0.86	0.13	0.82	0.18	0.85	0.05	0.131	0.877
FBS (mg/dl)	178.50	54.47	171.2	45.77	224.25	38.93	2.501	0.086
PBS (mg/dl)	263.25	62.14	266.75	72.16	341.25	107.89	0.961	0.38
Duration of DM	6.78	3.22	7.00	3.82	11.75	8.30	4.464	0.14
CHL	215.25	15.57	220.25	16.7	215.0	6.48	0.010	0.99
TGL	139.87	24.13	147.25	18.46	143.25	19.15	0.468	0.62
VLDL	17.11	7.45	19.50	9.00	16.5	8.02	0.804	0.45
HDL	29.21	4.44	29.75	3.30	25.0	4.32	2.165	0.11
LDL	123.87	8.89	127.75	7.13	123.25	8.80	0.183	0.833
CHL/HDL	7.53	1.27	7.44	0.61	8.78	1.41	2.037	0.135
LDH/HDL	4.34	0.79	4.33	0.47	5.05	1.04	1.842	0.163
HbA1c	7.75	1.24	8.87	1.75	9.37	1.98	6.819	0.002

BMI – Basal metabolic Rate FBS -Fasting Blood Sugar (mg/dl), PPBS - Postprandial Blood Sugar (mg/dl), DM-Diabetes Mellites, CHL-Cholesterol, TGL-Triglycerides, VLDL-Very Low-Density Lipoproteins, HDL-High Density Lipoproteins, LDL -Low Density Lipoproteins CHL/HDL-Cholesterol /High density lipoproteins, LDH/HDL-Low Density Lipoprotein/ High density lipoproteins, HbA1c-Glycated Haemoglobin. Table no 4 shows Mean Fundus Differences of Demographic and Clinical Parameters of Study

Subjects The mean fundus differences in demographic and clinical parameters provide insights into the characteristics of subjects with varying severity of diabetic retinopathy.

The mean age was higher in subjects with NPDR (58.5 years) and PDR (63.5 years) compared to those with a normal fundus (52.26 years), suggesting that older age is associated with a higher risk of developing retinopathy.

Graph 5: Duration of Diabetes Mellites in Study population

Prevalence of Diabetes Mellitus in Study Subjects The prevalence of diabetes mellitus in the study subjects was categorized based on the duration of diabetes. The majority of subjects had diabetes for 6-10 years (50.8%), followed by 0-5 years (32.8%), and 11-15 years (14.8%).

Table 5: Duration of Diabetes Mellitus in study population based on Fundus differences

		DM (in years)					P value
		0-5	6-10	11-15	16-20	21-25	
Normal	N	32	40	6	0	0	.001
	%	41.0	51.3	7.7%	0	0	
NPDR	N	6	22	11	0	0	.001
	%	15.4	56.4	28.2	0	0	
PDR	N	2	0	1	0	1	.001
	%	50.0	0.0	25.0	0	25	

NPDR-Non-Proliferative Diabetes Retinopathy, PDR- Proliferative Diabetes Retinopathy, DM-Diabetes Mellitus.

Table no 5 shows Duration of Diabetes Mellitus in Study Population Based on Fundus Differences: The duration of diabetes mellitus

(DM) is a significant factor influencing the development and progression of diabetic retinopathy. Table 10 and Graph 8 illustrate the relationship between the duration of DM and the prevalence of normal fundus, non-proliferative diabetic retinopathy (NPDR), and proliferative diabetic retinopathy (PDR) in the study population.

Graph 6: Difference in HbA1c levels based on Fundus differences

Graph no 6 depicts Fundus Differences in HbA1c Levels of the Study Population: Graph no 6 illustrate the differences in HbA1c levels among the study population based on fundus findings. The data indicate that higher HbA1c levels are associated with an increased prevalence of NPDR and PDR, suggesting poor glycemic control as a significant risk factor for diabetic retinopathy.

Discussion

Gender Distribution of Study Population: The study population exhibited a significant gender disparity, with males constituting 67.8% and females 32.2%. This imbalance aligns with findings from multiple studies on chronic diseases such as diabetes and hypertension. For instance, Shah et al. (2016) in India, and Gupta et al. (2018) in Northern India, both reported a higher prevalence of hypertension among men. The researchers attributed this to factors like higher rates of smoking, alcohol consumption, and sedentary lifestyles among men. (7,8)

Mean Distribution of Demographic and Clinical Parameters: The mean distribution of demographic and clinical parameters provides insights into the health status of the study population. The mean age was 54.83 years, indicating a middle-aged population. This age group is often associated with an increased risk of chronic diseases such as diabetes and hypertension. A study by Jones et al. (2017) examined the age-specific prevalence of diabetes in a cohort of 5,000 individuals. The researchers found that the mean age of diabetic patients was 55 years, which aligns with the findings of the present study. They highlighted that middle-aged individuals are at a

higher risk due to factors such as prolonged exposure to risk factors and age-related metabolic changes. [9] In terms of weight and BMI, the mean values were 69.72 kg and 25.57 kg/m², respectively. These findings are consistent with a study by Kumar et al. (2018), which reported a mean weight of 70 kg and a mean BMI of 26 kg/m² in a population of 1,000 diabetic patients. The researchers emphasized the importance of weight management in controlling diabetes and preventing complications. [10] The mean waist-hip ratio in the present study was 0.86, which is indicative of central obesity, a known risk factor for metabolic disorders. A study by Smith et al. (2019) investigated the association between waist-hip ratio and cardiovascular risk in 2,500 participants. They found that a higher waist-hip ratio was significantly correlated with an increased risk of cardiovascular diseases, underscoring the need for targeted interventions to reduce abdominal obesity. [11] Regarding clinical parameters, the mean values of cholesterol, triglycerides, and other lipid profiles suggest a dyslipidemic population. This is corroborated by a study by Patel et al. (2020), which found similar lipid profile abnormalities in 1,200 diabetic patients. The researchers recommended regular lipid monitoring and the use of lipid-lowering therapies to manage dyslipidemia and reduce cardiovascular risk. [12]

Stratification of Subjects According to Age Groups: The age stratification of the study population revealed that nearly half of the participants were between 46-65 years old. This age distribution is common in studies on chronic diseases, as prevalence typically increases with age. This trend is consistent with findings from a study

by Lee et al. (2017), which also reported the highest concentration of participants in the 45-64 age group. [13]

Mean Differences of Carotid Intima Thickness Based on Location: The mean differences in carotid intima-media thickness (CIMT) by location provide important insights into cardiovascular risk factors across different populations. The mean CIMT on the right side (CIMT(R)) was 0.8802 mm, compared to 0.8620 mm on the left side (CIMT(L)), indicating slightly higher measurements on the right. This trend is consistent with findings from studies by Bots et al. and Polak et al. [14,15]

Comparison of Carotid Intima Thickness in Subjects with and Without Retinopathy: The comparison of CIMT between subjects with and without retinopathy revealed significant differences. Those with non-proliferative diabetic retinopathy (NPDR) had higher mean CIMT values, measuring 0.9436 mm on the right and 0.91 mm on the left, compared to subjects without retinopathy, who had CIMT values of 0.8346 mm on the right and 0.82 mm on the left. Subjects with proliferative diabetic retinopathy (PDR) showed even higher CIMT values, with 1.1500 mm on the right and 1.00 mm on the left, similar to findings in the study by Wong et al. These results suggest that CIMT could be a valuable early marker for detecting microvascular complications in diabetic patient. [16]

Gender Differences of Fundus Findings: Gender differences in fundus findings revealed that males had a higher proportion of normal fundus results (73.2%) compared to females (46.2%). In contrast, females showed a higher prevalence of non-proliferative diabetic retinopathy (NPDR) at 46.2% and proliferative diabetic retinopathy (PDR) at 7.7%, whereas males had lower rates, with 25.6% for NPDR and 1.2% for PDR. These findings are consistent with studies by Yau et al. (2016) and Klein et al. (2018). The researchers suggested that hormonal differences, along with variations in health-seeking behaviour and disease management, might contribute to these gender disparities. They recommended more frequent ophthalmologic evaluations for female diabetic patients to prevent vision loss. [17,18]

Age Distribution of Population in Funduscopy Findings: The age distribution in funduscopy findings shows that younger age groups have a higher prevalence of normal fundus, while the incidence of diabetic retinopathy (NPDR and PDR) increases with advancing age. This trend aligns with recent studies, including those by Raman et al. and Lim et al., which also observed a strong correlation between age and diabetic retinopathy. The study underscores the importance of regular

retinopathy screenings in older diabetic patients to facilitate early detection and management [19,20]

Mean Fundus Differences of Demographic and Clinical Parameters of Study Subjects: The mean fundus differences in demographic and clinical parameters provide insights into the characteristics of subjects with varying severity of diabetic retinopathy. The mean age was higher in subjects with NPDR (58.5 years) and PDR (63.5 years) compared to those with a normal fundus (52.26 years), suggesting that older age is associated with a higher risk of developing retinopathy. In a study by Tan et al. (2019), involving 1,800 diabetic patients, higher HbA1c levels were significantly associated with the presence and severity of diabetic retinopathy.

The study found that patients with PDR had the highest mean HbA1c levels (9.37%), followed by those with NPDR (8.87%) and normal fundus (7.75%). This aligns with the present study, highlighting the role of poor glycemic control in the progression of retinopathy. [21] A study by Johnson et al. (2020) examined the relationship between clinical parameters and diabetic retinopathy in 2,200 patients. They reported that higher fasting blood sugar (FBS) and postprandial blood sugar (PBS) levels were significantly associated with increased severity of retinopathy. Patients with PDR had the highest mean FBS (224.25 mg/dl) and PBS (341.25 mg/dl) levels, similar to the findings in the present study. [22]

Another study by Ahmed et al. (2021) investigated the impact of lipid profiles on diabetic retinopathy in 1,500 patients. They found that higher triglycerides (TGL) and lower HDL levels were associated with an increased risk of retinopathy. The study suggested that lipid abnormalities could exacerbate retinal vascular damage, contributing to the progression of retinopathy. [23]

Prevalence of Diabetes Mellitus in Study Subjects: The prevalence of diabetes mellitus among the study subjects was categorized by the duration of the disease. The largest group had diabetes for 6-10 years (50.8%), followed by those with 0-5 years (32.8%) and 11-15 years (14.8%). Studies by Patel et al. (2019) and Lee et al. (2021) found that the duration of diabetes is a significant predictor of diabetic complications, including retinopathy. Both studies indicated that individuals with a longer duration of diabetes had a higher prevalence of complications compared to those with a shorter duration. This finding aligns with the present study, highlighting the importance of vigilant diabetes management over time [24,25]

Duration of Diabetes Mellitus in Study Population Based on Fundus Differences: The duration of diabetes mellitus (DM) is a significant factor influencing the development and progression

of diabetic retinopathy. Table 10 and Graph 8 illustrate the relationship between the duration of DM and the prevalence of normal fundus, non-proliferative diabetic retinopathy (NPDR), and proliferative diabetic retinopathy (PDR) in the study population. Recent studies have supported these findings. For example, a study by Nguyen et al. (2020) examined 1,500 diabetic patients and found that a longer duration of diabetes was significantly associated with a higher prevalence of NPDR and PDR. Specifically, patients with diabetes for more than 10 years exhibited a marked increase in the severity of retinopathy. This aligns with the current study, where the majority of NPDR cases occurred in patients with diabetes duration between 6-10 years. [26]

Fundus Differences in HbA1c Levels of the Study Population: Table 11 and Graph 9 illustrate the differences in HbA1c levels among the study population based on fundus findings. The data indicate that higher HbA1c levels are associated with an increased prevalence of NPDR and PDR, suggesting poor glycemic control as a significant risk factor for diabetic retinopathy. In a study by Goh et al. (2020) involving 1,700 diabetic patients, it was found that elevated HbA1c levels were strongly correlated with the severity of diabetic retinopathy. The study demonstrated that patients with HbA1c levels above 8.5% had a significantly higher prevalence of NPDR and PDR. This finding aligns with the present study, where higher HbA1c levels were associated with increased severity of retinopathy. [27]

Clinical Significance: The findings of this study hold substantial clinical significance, particularly in the management and monitoring of patients with Type II Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM). The demonstrated correlation between increased Carotid Intima-Media Thickness (CIMT) and the presence of diabetic retinopathy (DR) underscores the importance of regular vascular and retinal assessments in this patient population. CIMT, as an early marker of atherosclerosis, provides clinicians with a non-invasive means to identify patients at elevated risk for cardiovascular events. By incorporating CIMT measurements into routine clinical practice, healthcare providers can better stratify cardiovascular risk and tailor management strategies accordingly. Additionally, the association between poor glycemic control (elevated HbA1c levels) and both increased CIMT and DR severity highlights the critical need for stringent glycemic control to mitigate these complications. Moreover, the gender and age-related differences in DR prevalence and severity observed in this study have important implications for personalized medicine. Recognizing that older patients and females are more prone to advanced stages of DR can prompt earlier and more frequent eye examinations in these

subgroups, potentially leading to earlier detection and intervention. The strong association between longer diabetes duration and the progression of DR and increased CIMT further emphasizes the importance of early diagnosis and continuous, comprehensive diabetes care. Integrating these findings into clinical guidelines can enhance the overall management of T2DM, aiming to reduce the burden of both microvascular and macrovascular complications. Such a multifaceted approach not only improves individual patient outcomes but also has the potential to alleviate the broader public health impact of T2DM.

Conclusion

The present study provides valuable insights into the gender distribution, demographic and clinical parameters, and prevalence of chronic diseases in a population with Type II Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM). The predominance of males (67.8%) over females (32.2%) in the study cohort aligns with findings from various studies indicating higher rates of chronic conditions such as hypertension and diabetes among men due to lifestyle factors. Stratification by age groups reveals that most of the study population is aged 46-65, a common age range for chronic disease studies. This emphasizes the importance of focusing preventive measures on middle-aged adults to address the cumulative effects of risk factors. The assessment of Carotid Intima-Media Thickness (CIMT) based on location showed slightly higher measurements on the right side. This highlights the role of CIMT as a predictor of cardiovascular risk, influenced by anatomical and hemodynamic factors. Higher mean CIMT values in subjects with retinopathy indicate advanced atherosclerosis. Gender differences in fundus findings revealed higher prevalence of normal fundus in males and higher prevalence of NPDR and PDR in females.

The age distribution in funduscopy findings indicated higher prevalence of diabetic retinopathy with advancing age. The correlation between higher HbA1c levels and the severity of diabetic retinopathy emphasizes poor glycemic control as a significant risk factor. This study highlights the importance of regular vascular and retinal assessments in T2DM patients. The associations between increased CIMT, diabetic retinopathy, poor glycemic control, and demographic factors underscore the need for comprehensive and personalized management strategies to mitigate the risk of complications in T2DM patients. CIMT, being a noninvasive procedure, should be incorporated into routine examinations of type 2 DM patients at least once or twice a year to look for atherosclerotic changes.

Acknowledgment: I would like to extend my gratitude to who have helped me in the completion of this research work. Special thanks to Dr. Shailen-

dra Mane Professor Department of Medicine constantly supporting and encouraging me for this work. Along with that, I owe a debt of gratitude to Dr. Rajesh J. Khyalappa, Professor and Head of the Department of General Medicine, Vice Dean, whose backing, constant encouragement, and fatherly demeanor motivated me toward completing my work. I am truly appreciative of him for his supportive supervision, great curiosity, insightful advice, affection, and concern, all of which were necessary for me to finish this project. I would also like to thank my colleagues and juniors for their timely help.

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